

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

I am very happy to announce the fifth regular issue of 2024. In this issue, 7 articles by 21 authors from 8 countries (Austria, Brazil, France, India, Iran, Morocco, Pakistan, and Turkey) cover a variety of topical research aspects in computer science. Allow me to express my appreciation to all authors for their sound research and to the editorial board and guest reviewers for the highly valuable reviews and comments for improvement. This continuous stream of relevant and novel contributions, along with the generous support of the consortium members, sustains the quality of our journal.

In the ongoing effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles or special issues for our journal.

In the fifth regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following seven accepted articles: Florian Skopik, Arndt Bonitz, Daniel Slamanig, Markus Kirschner, and Wolfgang Hacker from Austria focus on cybersecurity issues and aim to deliver a concept for a device that can be used in multiple security domains, isolating mission-specific data from each other without the risk of data spillover, and based on this, outline a high-level concept for a resilient single device concept that is able to withstand common intrusion attempts. Yunus Emre Avcı and Adem Tuncer from Turkey propose their model for detecting lane changes by applying a wavelet transform to high-resolution data from unmanned aerial vehicles based on empirical lane changing data from pNEUMA. Alaor Cervati Neto and Alexandre L. M. Levada from Brazil cover in their article improvements to the Locality Preserving Projections (LPP) algorithm by incorporating a recently proposed graph inference method called Probabilistic Nearest Neighbors (PNN), an extension of the Clustering with Adaptive Neighbors (CAN) approach. In a collaboration between researchers from Morocco and France, Ayoub Charef, Zahi Jarir, and Mohamed Quafafou discuss their approach, which utilizes computer vision algorithms to detect and quantify traffic violations by motorcyclists, such as non-compliance with helmet regulations, illegal lane changing, driving in the wrong direction, weaving between vehicles and running red lights. Razieh Dehghani and Raman Ramsin from Iran propose an evaluation framework for Situational Method Engineering processes and guidelines for improvements as well as for knowledge management support. Saima Farhan, Rubiya Shoukat and Aqsa Aslam from Pakistan address the detection of sarcastic remarks from a multi-domain dataset by using a Bi-LSTM model that works with pre-trained GloVe

word embeddings. Binu Paul, Dwijen Rudrapal, and Kunal Chakma from India cover a comprehensive survey on multimodal machine translation approaches for Indian languages.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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